

STRUCTURE OF AN OPTIMAL MANAGEMENT MODEL OF REGIONAL TOURISM DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract: This article highlighted the most important prerequisite for creating a system of the optimal management model of regional tourism development, the theory of optimal development of the regional economy and the consistent application of the principle of optimality to management.

Keywords: optimal management, development of economic sectors, price, profit, profitability, material incentives, resources (systematic approach), cycle of principles

Today, the theory of optimal development of the regional economy is the most important prerequisite for creating a system of optimal regional tourism management. Its main feature is the consistent application of the principle of optimality to the regulation and management of economic processes in the region. The theory of optimal development based on the determination of the objective criteria of the optimal development of tourism in the region, the theory of optimal development, the problems of comparative comparison of production results and costs in terms of quality and quantity, the rational comparison and use of limited labor and material resources, the optimal pace and proportionality of the development of economic sectors, production facilities and the problems of integration of the interests of the whole society are studied.

Models should be based on the accumulated experience of regulating and managing the economy. They need to be given the most effective and optimal results at all levels, from a small tourist enterprise to the regional level. At the same time, the need to ensure maximum use of economic opportunities of complex rational management of models should be taken into account in the following aspects of services and products provided in the field. Price, profit, profitability, material incentive only in this case the optimal decision is combined with optimal conditions and incentives for its implementation. Adding goals is done in several steps. First of all, the goal is set according to the discussed or forecast requirements. Then the resources to achieve it are searched (systematic approach) and finally all the resources that can be attracted are determined, the goal and the period of its achievement are determined (genetic approach). The goals of the lower and higher level systems should be compatible with each other and directed towards achieving the next, that is, the goals of the lower level system combined with the goals of the higher level system forms its purpose. Figure 1

Figure 1. The optimal management model of regional tourism development

The regional economy should be based on the use of three main principles:

❖ **first of all** to be able to carefully calculate the requirements of the population of the region, the state and dynamics of emerging markets, the requirements of the state and individual production entities;

❖ **secondly**, creation of conditions for maximal adaptation of regions to internal and external factors and economic structures; thirdly, to actively satisfy the interests of the region.

The conceptual basis of the complex numerical models of forecasting the economic dynamics of the region, the theory of sustainable economic growth, increasing the competitiveness of the region, etc. were used. Tourist formality, placing the national market of tourist services as one of the leading tourist destinations. The means of implementation of the integration vector is the use of international cooperation in the field of tourism to strengthen mutual understanding and trust between countries, the use of tourism for the development of mutually beneficial and parity economic, trade, diplomatic relations, favorable conditions for the exchange of tourists, the organization of technical cooperation and the simplification of tourist formalities.

The principle of continuity- is to determine the management of the development of the tourism services market as a continuous process based on the need for constant monitoring of the external environment and the transformational changes of the spatial and polarization factors affecting the formation of the market. these changes create the need to constantly adjust, adjust or clarify the goals and strategic priorities.

The principle of efficiency- implies effective use of both internal conditions of market development - organizational and economic; socio-economic, natural-climatic and cultural,

historical and foreign - effective international cooperation on a bilateral and multilateral basis.

Planning principle- defines the main directions and strategic priorities, prepares an action program and implements it on the basis of ensuring the proportional development of each element of the system, according to the priority of its impact. implementation of goals and achieving the main goal of the concept.

The principle of expediency- takes into account the possibility of setting specific goals, their achievement and implementation, as well as the ratio with the necessary resources. The principle of hierarchy is to determine the sequence of subordination of elements and links, and to form the interaction between the levels of formation and management of the market of tourist services. The level of the hierarchy depends on the forms of management, which is of particular importance in the implementation of the integration vector. The principle of scientificity (scientific validity) is the need to apply new concepts of science, advanced experience of international and regional organizations, advanced trends and new forms of management in the system and mechanism of tourism market formation.

Complementarity principle- this is the need to take into account the possibility of tourism goods and services being comprehensive, because the purchase of one tourist product or service leads to the need to purchase all types of services and goods. The principle of substitutability consists in the possibility of free exchange of individual tourist services that make up the complex tourist product, as well as the tourist product as a whole. This leads to increased competition between market entities, constant monitoring of tourist motives and preferences, updating of the offer of goods and services in the market, formation of large-scale measures to attract and retain customers.

In addition to the four main functions of the management process, namely: planning, organization, motivation and control, management of the development of the tourism services market requires the formation of a specific set of functions that ensure the achievement of goals. and objectives of the concept. Specific functions within the proposed concept:

- ❖ planning a high-quality tourist product offer taking into account consumer requirements;
- ❖ control over the quality of the production of complex tourist products and the provision of tourist services in order to make a decision on the development of new tourist and recreation areas;
- ❖ coordination of mutual cooperation of tourist services market entities providing standardization and certification of products, services, management;
- ❖ ensure the development and implementation of normative and legal documents;
- ❖ financial credit, investment promotion, preferential support of market entities.

Financial support of the tourism sector is an important issue in the development of the market of tourism services, and to solve it, in our opinion, the following is necessary:

- ensure the appropriate level of public and private management, as well as precise coordination of actions of republican and local control bodies;
- support the development of private initiatives in the tourist services market;
- developing an effective incentive system
- tourist product to domestic and foreign markets;

- accepts the necessary legal documents
- issues of investment and taxation in the field of tourism;
- the procedure for further improvement of foreign tourists of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
- forming the information space of the tourism industry, etc.

The competitive development of the tourism services market serves as a fundamental basis for the development and implementation of its development strategy. In general, in order to achieve the goals of tourism services market development, in our opinion, it is necessary to ensure the following:

- the coherence of tourism policy at the national and regional level and clearly defining the powers and responsibilities of all parties interested in the development of tourism: the private sector, professional non-governmental organizations and the state of the local community;
- introducing a horizontal and vertical integrated institution of social partnership: state, private sector and their professional associations and associations.

Thus, solving the problems of effective tourism development can significantly increase the flow of tourists to Uzbekistan and cash flows to the country's economy, as well as, on the one hand, provide an increase in tax deductions for budgets at different levels. and increase the employment of tourists, and on the other hand, the development of regions and adjacent regions. economic sectors. All this increases the role of international tourism in the economy of Uzbekistan, creates conditions for the development of the national economy, and the quality of life of tourists. The optimal solution is to create a mechanism for the development of tourism services in the region.

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